

Synthesis of Possible Antiamoebic Agents

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Synthesis of ω -(3-alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-amylamines has been effected with a view to testing their amoebicidal activity according to the scheme: 2-alkylanisole $\rightarrow$ γ -(3-alkyl-4-methoxybenzoyl)-*n*-butyric acid $\rightarrow$ δ -(3-alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-valeric acid $\rightarrow$ δ -(3-alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-valeramide $\rightarrow$ ω -(3-alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-amylamine.

Sawhney and Kachru¹⁻³ synthesised γ -(3-alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-propylamines (I: $n=3$) and δ -(3-alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-butylamines (I: $n=4$) which were tested by Kaushiva³ for *in vitro* amoebicidal activity. The activity was found to increase in both the series with rise in the molecular weight and further the δ -aminos (I: $n=4$) seemed to exhibit more enhanced activity than the γ -analogue (I: $n=3$). This indicates that the activity increases with the distance of the amino group from the aromatic nucleus.

Based on these observations, it was considered worthwhile to ascertain the effect of removal of the basic amino group in the compound (I: $n=4$) further away from the nucleus by one carbon atom (I: $n=5$) on the amoebicidal activity. This would also provide an opportunity to make a comparative study of the activity of this group of compounds with those of type (II), already reported in a previous communication⁴.

Synthesis of compounds of type (I: $n=5$) has been made according to the following scheme:

1. *This Journal*, 1959, 36, 121, 486.
2. *Curr. Sci.*, 1959, 28, 365.
3. *Ann. Biochem. Expt. Med.*, 1960, 20, Suppl. 380.
4. Sreedharan and Sharma, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.* 1965, 28, 141.

The *o*-alkylanisole is subjected to the Friedel-Crafts reaction with glutaric anhydride in nitrobenzene to obtain the acids of type (B) in 60 to 68% yields. Reduction of the keto-acids to the acids of type (C) was effected by the Huang-Minlon⁵ method in 68 to 76% yields. The acids of type (C) were converted to the amides (D) by passing ammonia gas into the molten acids at 180° in 68-74% yields. Finally the amides were reduced to the required amines by $LiAlH_4$ by the usual method in satisfactory yields.

*EXPERIMENTAL

γ-(3-Alkyl-4-methoxybenzoyl)-*n*-butyric Acids (B).—Anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.7*M*) and glutaric anhydride (0.35*M*) were dissolved in nitrobenzene (200 ml), cooled in ice to 0°, and mechanically stirred while alkylanisole (0.35*M*) was added portionwise during 1 hr. Stirring was continued for 4 hr. more. During this time the temperature was allowed to rise gradually to the room temperature and then left overnight. Subsequent operations were the same as described for *β*-(3-ethyl-4-methoxybenzoyl)propionic acid⁶. Analytical data, m.p., yield, etc. are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

γ-(3-Alkyl-4-methoxybenzoyl)-*n*-butyric acids (B).

R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
Me	126°	68 %	$C_{13}H_{16}O_4$	C: 66.01 % H: 6.80	66.08 % 6.83
Et	104°	65	$C_{14}H_{18}O_4$	C: 67.12 H: 7.12	67.15 7.24
<i>n</i> -Pr	98°	60	$C_{15}H_{20}O_4$	C: 68.01 H: 7.55	68.15 7.62
<i>n</i> -Bu	94°	64	$C_{16}H_{22}O_4$	C: 69.01 H: 8.01	69.03 8.11

δ-(3-Alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-valeric Acids (C).—A mixture of acid (B), (0.2*M*), KOH (40 g.), diethylene glycol (300 ml), and hydrazine hydrate (85%, 25 ml) was refluxed for 1½ hr. The condenser was removed until the temperature had reached 195-200°, when refluxing was continued for 4 hr. longer. The solution was cooled, diluted with water, acidified with 6*N*-HCl, and extracted with ether. On removal of the ether, the product was remethylated with KOH and dimethyl sulphate;

* All melting and boiling points are uncorrected.

6. J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1948, 68, 2487.

5. Sawhney and Kachru, this Journal, 1959, 36, 121.

the resulting product was recrystallised from petroleum (60-80°). Compounds thus prepared are listed in Table II.

TABLE II

 δ -(3-Alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-valeric acids (C).

R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
Me	86°	70 %	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ O ₃	C: 70.2% H: 8.12	70.24% 8.16
Et	82°	73	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₃	C: 71.01 H: 8.44	71.11 8.53
<i>n</i> -Pr	78°	68	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₃	C: 71.80 H: 8.84	71.06 8.85
<i>n</i> -Bu	75°	71	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₃	C: 72.62 H: 9.14	72.69 9.15

δ -(3-Alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-valeramides (D).—Dry NH₃ gas was passed through the molten acid (C) (0.13 *M*) at 180° for 2 hr. The mass was cooled, washed with dry ether, and crystallised from anhydrous ethanol. Analytical data, m.p., and yields of the compounds prepared are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

 δ -(3-Alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-valeramides (D).

R'	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
Me	104°	78 %	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	C: 70.38 % H: 8.61 N: 6.21	70.55 8.65 6.33
Et	102°	75	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	C: 71.32 H: 8.92 N: 6.03	71.45 8.99 6.04
<i>n</i> -Pr	107°	74	C ₁₅ H ₂₃ O ₂ N	C: 72.21 H: 9.18 N: 5.60	72.25 9.29 5.61
<i>n</i> -Bu	101°	70	C ₁₆ H ₂₅ O ₂ N	C: 73.03 H: 9.52 N: 5.23	73.96 9.58 5.31

ω -(3-Alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-amylamines (I; $n = 5$).—The amide (D) (0.05 *M*) was reduced to the respective amine (I), using LiAlH₄ (0.08 *M*) and anhydrous ether (200 ml) in the usual manner. Refluxing was done for 12 hr. Analytical data, m.p., yields of the compounds prepared are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

ω-(3-Alkyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-amylamines (I: *n*=5).

R.	B.P.	Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
Me	152°/1mm	63 %	C ₁₃ H ₂₁ ON	C: 75.21 % H: 10.18 N: 6.71	75.31% 10.21 6.75
Et	155°/1	60	C ₁₄ H ₂₃ ON	C: 75.87 H: 10.35 N: 6.18	75.97 10.45 6.33
<i>n</i> -Pr	182°/2	68	C ₁₅ H ₂₅ ON	C: 76.41 H: 10.58 N: 5.82	76.54 10.70 5.95
<i>n</i> -Bu	186°/2	67	C ₁₆ H ₂₇ ON	C: 77.10 H: 10.82 N: 5.48	77.05 10.91 5.61

*Hydrochloride m.p. 114°, 101° respectively.

The *amine picrates* were prepared by mixing saturated solutions of picric acid and amine in ethanol and recrystallised from dilute ethanol in yellow prisms. Similar compounds prepared are listed in Table V.

TABLE V

Amine picrates.

R.	M.P.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.		%Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Me	132°	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₄	52.38	52.49	5.52	5.56	12.74	12.83
Et	160°	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₄	53.16	53.32	5.75	5.81	12.21	12.43
<i>n</i> -Pr	152°	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ O ₈ N ₄	54.21	54.30	6.02	6.07	12.01	12.05
<i>n</i> -Bu	143°	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ O ₈ N ₄	55.12	55.21	6.26	6.31	11.63	11.71

The *amine hydrochlorides* were prepared by passing dry HCl gas through amine in anhydrous ether and recrystallised from a mixture of anhydrous ethanol and ethyl acetate.

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